

CONFERENCE ABSTRACT

A case report of peroneal neuropathy

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Introduction

Peroneal neuropathy is the most common mononeuropathy found in the lower extremities. It may be the result of habitual leg crossing or other prolonged posture, ankle orthoses, leg casting, inflammatory disease, surgery or trauma. Electromyography is a very useful tool for both diagnosis and follow-up of recovery.

Clinical case

The authors report a case of a 14-year-old adolescent with intellectual disability and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, medicated with methylphenidate and followed in a Neurodevelopment consultation.

He was admitted in the emergency department due to paresthesia of the right foot with limited dorsiflexion with 5 days of evolution that began after spending a few hours on the sofa with crossed legs. On physical examination he presented a decrease in strength in the right leg, marked decrease in dorsiflexion of the right foot in decubitus, and in tactile sensitivity in the anterior aspect of the right leg and foot.

Considering all medical history and physical examination he performed an electromyography that showed right peroneal neuropathy with partial axonal injury with indication of reinnervation and without active denervation. He was diagnosed with peroneal neuropathy and began physical therapy with gradual recovery of motor and sensory deficits.

Conclusion

Prompt recognition and diagnosis are essential to preserve nerve function. There is no consensus in the literature regarding the optimal treatment. Initially, treatment can be conservative for most peroneal nerve injuries. Many patients benefit from nonsurgical measures, including activity modification, physical therapy, and medications.

The prognosis of compressive peroneal nerve neuropathy in children is usually good, especially with idiopathic compression, when spontaneous recovery usually occurs within a few months of symptom onset.

Keywords: Peroneal neuropathy; electromyography; practice guideline; schools; child; adolescent

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